

LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOR AND ADVERSITY QUOTIENT OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS

EMILIANA MADLANGBAYAN ROXAS¹, NERRIE E. MALALUAN, Ed.D.²

<https://orchid.org/0000-0001-5939-8744>¹

emiliana.roxas@g.batstate-u.edu.ph¹

Department of Education

Philippines

ABSTRACT

The study assessed the leadership behavior and adversity quotient® of public elementary school administrators in the Division of Batangas, Philippines. It aimed to describe the leadership behaviors of the respondents in terms of embracing aspects like personality, leadership style, learning environment, technology, and in the organizational composition and strength as well as measured the respondents' adversity quotient® along the components of control, ownership, reach and endurance. With the use of the descriptive method survey questionnaire and interview was conducted from 232 public elementary school administrators. Findings revealed that public elementary administrators greatly manifested the leadership behavior of being appreciative in every accomplishment made by the members of the team and the ethical behavior in advocating transparency and accountability in the school management for both in their personality and the leadership style respectively. On the other hand, the respondents manifested to a great extent as well the following leadership behaviors, transparency in providing open communication platforms for parents, stockholders and the public and are greatly focused on achieving school goals for safe teaching-learning environment, open-mindedness in learning new skills utilizing technology and being honest and transparent in updating school's transparency board to inform stakeholders on the MOOE disbursements, canteen reports, PTA financial reports. Also, it was revealed that the respondents' adversity quotient in terms of control and endurance dimensions is all below average while ownership and reach registered low level. There were significant differences in respondents' leadership behavior in terms of personality and their adversity quotient in the dimension of endurance and in the dimension of control in terms of the learning. The findings served as the bases in developing a management plan to enhance the leadership capabilities of the public elementary school administrators in Division of Batangas.

Keywords: Leadership Behavior, Adversity Quotient®, Management Plan, Governance, Basic Education Act